

Current state and possible directions of improvement of handling system of wastes being formed on water transport vessels

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Abstract

The World Ocean is the source of enormous wealth used by the mankind in its interests. It forms the weather on the planet, enables passengers and cargos transportation by vessels of water transport (WT). Along with this, the human vigorous activities on its development/use cause significant harm to it through pollution including that at operation of WT ships, which account for about 12% of all pollutants of the water environment. The wastewater released by ships carrying passengers is also dangerous pollutants, since this sewage is released without any treatment, causing the proliferation of algae and depleting the oxygen of the waters. There are also hydrocarbons that make the water get greasy, making marine life almost impossible. If it fools anyone who thinks the pollution caused by them to in marine life. Giants also emit substances harmful to human life, such as sulfate, which is highly dangerous and can be lodged in important organs such as the lungs. With regard to human health, the populations are most affected by coastal areas, mainly residents of port cities, where there is constant traffic of maritime vessels. From the point of view of systematic approach to available data analysis, the article describes the current state of pollution of the water environment by wastes being formed because of the water transport vessels operation. The existing structure of the system of shipboard wastes handling is presented as well as the used techniques and technical means. Their disadvantages are shown. Possible directions of improvement of the existing system of ship wastes handling are proposed, though the further special studies are needed.

Keywords: Water transport, Shipboard wastes, Requirements, Wastes handling, Directions of improvement.

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1. Introduction

The World Ocean is the source of enormous wealth used by the mankind in its interests. It forms the weather on the planet, enables passengers and cargos transportation by vessels of water transport (WT). Along with this, the human vigorous activities on its development/use cause significant harm to it through pollution including that at operation of WT ships, which account for about 12% of all pollutants of the water environment (WE).

Since the 60s of the last century, the issue of pollution prevention of the waters of the oceans began to be systematically addressed in frame of International Maritime Organization (IMO) at UN, at the initiative of which a number of important documents in the field of the WE pollution prevention were adopted. In Russian Federation (RF), the problem of WE pollution prevention is regulated by a number of laws, regulations and orders of the RF Government. Among other regulations, the RF Transport Strategy for the period up to 2030 defines the need to ensure the environmental safety (ES) of waste management of the transportation industry. In relation to WT, it means the ES protection in ships operation, prevention of water pollution from ships with the household effluents and oily waters, oil and other substances harmful to human health and aquatic biological resources.

This article is aimed at a systematic analysis of the available literature references/sources in the field of the prevention of the WE pollution with ship wastes, an overall picture presentation of its real state and – finally – suggestion of possible ways of the current state improvement.

2. Development

According to the wording of the UN International Convention on global environment (GE) (1972) and UN convention on the maritime law (1982), under WE pollution, the following is meant: “The human activities resulted in direct or indirect penetration of substances or energy into WE (including estuaries), which causes or may cause such harmful effects as harm to living resources and life at sea, human health jeopardizing, obstacles to maritime activities including fishing and other lawful sea waters use ways, sea water

quality worsening and deterioration of recreational conditions”.

The main sources of WE pollution are the following wastes being formed during WT ships operation [1]: oily water (OW), effluent water (EW) and garbage.

During ships operation, OW can be formed in the following forms:

- ❖ bilge water (BW) accumulated due to leakages of fuels and oils under floorboards of engine rooms;
- ❖ fuel separation wastes during operation of ship power plants (SPP);
- ❖ wastes resulted from cleaning of holds or tanks after transportation of oil products.

Under the floorboards of a ship, OW is mixed with the incoming mechanical impurities: paint particles, fluff from crumbling of various insulation and stuffing materials (during vibration and sea rolling), corrosion products, coked oil products, etc. In addition, BW is contaminated with chemical impurities in the form of surfactants, sulfur-containing compounds and organic acids. BW contains fuel in amount of 70-80%, oil of 20-30% and mechanical impurities up to 4-6%. The amount of oil contained in BW is on average not less than 2000 ppm (parts per million) for vessels with a diesel engine and 1500 ppm for those with a steam turbine engine. Depending on a ship's displacement of water, the formed on it BW amount can make from 0.3-8.0 to 30-50 m³ daily [1].

The effluents being formed on the ships can be virtually divided onto household fecal sewage and household hygienic effluents [1].

To the shipboard household fecal EW, the following waters belong:

- ❖ drains and other outflows from all types of toilets, urinals, bowls and scuppers in shared lavatories;
- ❖ drains from sinks, baths, showers and scuppers situated in medical premises;
- ❖ outflows from areas, where animals are kept;
- ❖ other effluents if they are mixed with the effluents listed above.

On its composition, the fecal EW consists of 58% of organic and 42% of mineral substances (20% of

them are represented by insoluble substances in the form of suspended particles). This kind of effluents contains the following main contaminating components: pathogenic bacteria, viruses; dissolved organic and mineral substances featuring with a medium-high biochemical oxygen demand; solid particles deposited on the bottom and absorbing oxygen during biochemical decomposition; floating particles located on the surface of water, which absorb sunlight and represent a serious problem for aquatic biocenoses; nutrients (phosphorus and nitrogen compounds), presence of which leads to the so-called "flowering" of water basins.

To the household hygienic EW, the following kinds belong: wastewaters from sinks, showers, tubs, residential scuppers and sanitary-hygienic premises, from sinks/equipment of galleys and other areas of the catering departments.

In global scale, the EW discharge from ships into open sea and special sea areas is regulated by rules of Appendix IV of the MARPOL-73/78 Convention and HELCOM-92 Convention. In the RF internal and territorial waters, it is regulated by RF Law on environment protection.

In the RF internal and territorial waters, EW discharge from ships is allowed in the following cases:

- ❖ EW is purified and disinfected; its discharge is done in limits of I and II belts of the sanitary zones after their treatment in an installation, parameters of cleaning and disinfection of which meets the following standards: on coli-index not more than 2500, on BOD₅ (biological oxygen demand in 5 days) not more than 50 mg/l; suspended solids content not more than 100 mg/l above the same in the washing water;
- ❖ The discharge is made when the vessel is moving at a speed of at least 4 knots and causes neither visible floating solids nor changes in the color of the surrounding water.

By the Rule I of MARPOL-73/78 Appendix V, it is determined that the garbage formed on ships means all types of food, household and operational wastes, all types of plastics, cargo residues and ash from incinerators, which are formed during the normal ship operation and are subjected to constant or periodic removal.

The permitted amount of wastes per person on a ship is determined by a type of a ship, its size and

a total number of people on the ship. According to IMO, the average daily rate of household garbage makes 1-2 kg/person on cargo ships and 2-3 kg/person on passenger ships.

The summary results of the garbage formation study on passenger ships show that the components of garbage are divided as follows [1]: food wastes 62.2%; paper/cardboard 17%; glass 8%; textiles 3.5%; metal 5%; household wastes 2.4%; wooden wastes 1.5%; plastic wastes 0.3%; rubber/rust/paint 0.1%.

The garbage discharge from ships in open sea and special aquatic areas is determined by the Rules of MARPOL-73/78 (Appendix V) and in internal and territorial waters by national rules and legislations of coastal states.

The currently established system of organization, technological solutions and applied technical means (TM) of shipboard wastes handling does not meet in full the modern international and national requirements on the protection of the water environment safety (WE ES) in course of ships navigation.

According to the requirements of Russian River Register and Sanitary Regulations and Standards 2.5.2-703-98, the existing system of shipboard wastes handling allows the following two methods of pollutants (OW, EW and garbage) removal from ships:

- ❖ disposal to outer (coastal or floating) water protection TM;
- ❖ re-processing and/or neutralization of pollutants directly on vessel board with help of a special shipboard equipment.

The procedure for the implementation of these options depends on the navigation area of the vessel, the type of vessel, the number and capacity of receiving points, ships-collectors or ship overall wastes re-processors (SOWR) and requirements imposed on quality of the discharged OW, EW & garbage.

In particular, the variant with the wastes disposal onto the outer TM is preferable for rather small auxiliary ships and ships performing short travels with frequent stops and a small number of people on board.

For large passenger and cargo ships, the second wastes handling option is preferable. In this case, stations are installed on board for OW cleaning (OWC) and EW cleaning and disinfection

(EWCD) as well as furnaces (boilers)-incinerators.

The shipboard stations of OW cleaning are rather expensive and energy-intensive kinds of equipment, the use of which is not economically feasible. By the conducted research, the possibility was shown of OW using after its preliminary cleaning on shipboard standard equipment as water of not high quality suitable for water-fuel emulsion (WFE) of boilers and incinerators.

Especially economically feasible is the OW use in WFE boilers on large passenger ships and oil-tankers, where the operating time of auxiliary boilers and incinerators is up to 50% of the operating time of the main engines. The share of water for WFE boilers can be raised to 38%, which leads to a slight fall in boiler efficiency; however the entire volume of OW can be disposed of by combustion [3].

According to the type of cleaning and disinfection, EW processing methods are divided into three types: mechanical, biochemical and physical-chemical.

The based on the mechanical method shipboard systems work with the stations of EWCD of the type "HL-CONT" (Western Germany) [2]. The main disadvantage of the latter is the lack of filtration at the final stage of processing, which can lead to the discharge of contaminated water overboard.

On the basis of the biochemical method, such stations work as "BioCompact" and "Ka-Rea" (Germany), Trident (UK) and "Unex-Simultan" (Finland). They have a number of drawbacks hindering their wider application [4, 5], some of which can be eliminated by the bio-estimation method consisting in process control and regulation of the water quality formation [6]. In the recent years, the new direction in biological EW treatment has been actively developed called SBR technology [7]. As it is envisioned by the authors [8], this technology allows all stages of EW purification to be carried out in one tank sequentially on a certain time-based algorithm. This would enable eliminating the secondary and often also initial stages of sedimentation from the technological scheme and not using the pumping equipment for the activated sludge return, which reduces the energy consumption of the system and makes the cleaning system more compact.

The EWCD stations working based on the physical-chemical methods are most prevalent in WT due to their small mass-dimensional characteristics in comparison to the same at biochemical purification and also due to their high efficiency in waste water treatment [4].

On inland navigation vessels, based on physical-chemical methods of EW re-processing, such EWSD stations are used as "Neptumatic" (Sweden), "MOS-75" (Austria), "Mini-L-Frame" (UK), "Stok" (Russia) and "EOS" (Russia) [9].

Figure 1. Modern fishing boats and ships pollute the seas and cargo ship waste dumping in the ocean.

Source: [10].

The EW electrochemical processing takes place in the "EOS"-type plants. The effect is achieved due to the electrochemical formation of active chlorine in the node of fine cleaning as well as under the action of the electric field. Recently, the methods of UV irradiation [2, 5] and thermal oxidation [11, 12] have been used as alternative methods of disinfection as they allow creating systems of circulating water supply, thereby reducing the overboard discharge amount of the treated effluents. A significant disadvantage of the EW electrochemical treatment is the use of chlorine-containing reagents, though this one can be eliminated by the method of fine cleaning with aid of membranes [8].

The physical EW disinfection methods are more environmentally friendly and cost-effective than the chemical ones. After all, we should not underestimate the fact that over time, microorganisms develop resistance to various influences. In particular, it has been shown [13]

that over the past 20 years, the bacteria and viruses resistance to chlorine has increased 6 times and to ultraviolet 4 times.

In the worldwide and domestic practice, several methods of re-processing of shipboard garbage are adopted such as: the bio-thermal processing; the separation of solid wastes on fractions with subsequent briquetting; the milling with the subsequent dissolution in water; the chemical treatment with solvents; and the thermal combustion.

The most optimal and acceptable for shipboard conditions method is the thermal processing of garbage. It allows processing all types of shipboard wastes, significantly reducing their weight and volume; besides, the resulting ash and slag are packaged and handed over to the shore for further use. The disposal of the shipboard wastes is carried out with aid of the special device for the thermal disposal, which is the incinerator.

The mentioned literature materials concerned the problem state in the area of the shipboard wastes handling allow proposing some possible ways of reduction of the water transport ecological loads on WE.

In particular, the EW discharge amounts reduction is needed. The EW amount on ships is directly dependent on water consumption. Hence, it is possible to reduce the ships impact on the WE EW by reduction of water consumption or creation of recycling systems. Notably, the creation of recycling systems is considered to be more preferable. Even as early as in the 70s, the industrialized countries of the world began to apply the reuse of purified EW in industry and agriculture [1, 14, 15]. Directly on ships, the recycling systems can be applied as the secondary water suppliers for the following needs: toilets flushing, feeding of boilers of low pressure, cooling and power supply (SPP) systems and gas treatment plants (for the "wet" gas treatment methods use).

As for the water consumption reduction on ships, this is possible to be done – especially in the hot period of the year – by creation of an artificial pleasant microclimate in residential and office premises with aid of air conditioning systems and by introduction of small swimming pools on ships, which would lead to a sufficiently large reduction in the consumption of the drinking (high quality) water in showers, and thus this measure would reduce the EW amount.

Taking into account the high cost and significant weight and size characteristics of TM for OW cleaning, some specialists propose using OW after pretreatment in WFE of boilers and incinerators [11, 16]. This proposal will allow not only dispensing with the OW cleaning equipment at all but also reducing the amount of harmful substances in the exhaust gases of boilers.

Currently, on the one hand, the requirements on ES maintenance have become stricter and on the other hand the impossibility is evident to fulfill these requirements in frame of the existing system of shipboard wastes handling, especially with aid of the existing TM. In the established conditions, the most preferable is the transition to the integrated system of ES maintenance on WT vessels [16-18]. The essence of this system is to carry out the effective purification of liquids and gases formed on ships due to use of universal techniques for processing of various media with markedly different initial characteristics.

3. Discussion

Generally, the shipboard TM ensuring the ES can be grouped based on quality parameters of the initial substances and the finished products. For example, one of the groups may include EW purification systems (EW-PS) and gas purification systems of SPP (G-PS). On the same principle, in the second group, TM can be combined for the preparation and further use of OW and purified EW for various household and production purposes. In turn, both of these TM groups can be combined into a single complex, in which after its use in household-technical purposes, the water is collected into the EW tank, where it is prepared for further purification and sedimentation [17]. From the tank, the pre-cleaned EW is pumped to the EWSD station, where it is finally cleaned and disinfected. The treated effluents are divided into two streams: the main part of the water is sent to the tank of the secondary water supply, while the unclaimed part of the water is discharged overboard. The water of secondary (technical) quality is used for toilets flushing, gas cleaning, feeding of the cooling equipment, heat supply systems and boilers as well as for the preparation of WFE for diesel engines.

The OW resulted from SPP operation is completely burned in the furnaces of boilers (both auxiliary and incinerators' ones), where it is fed as a component of WFE. The accumulated garbage

including EW and OW sediments (sludge) is eliminated in incinerators. Mainly, the SPP exhaust gases after their cleaning, neutralization and cooling are emitted into the atmosphere, though a part of them (about 10%) is returned to SPP (for recirculation).

Thus, in the proposed approach to the integrated shipboard wastes treatment, the systems (including the recycling system) of SPP exhaust gases cleaning and the OW and garbage elimination by burning are combined into a common core and interconnected.

4. Conclusions and proposals

The current system of WT shipboard wastes handling ensures the ES of ships operation for WE not to the fullest extent from the point of view of the international and national requirements level.

The used technical means have sufficiently large weight and size characteristics and are featured with significant energy consumption, which affects the ships operational efficiency. The chemical reagents used in TM for decontamination are quite toxic and require compliance with appropriate control and safety measures, both during the technological processes of wastes detoxification and at discharging of the resulted products into the environment.

The possible ways of improvement of the existing system of shipboard wastes handling are as follows and anyway they require further special studies:

- ❖ finding ways, methods and TM for reduction of water consumption on ships or creation of recycling systems;
- ❖ application of environmentally friendly reagents and techniques of their application for the measures implementation of the disposal of wastes formed on ships;
- ❖ methods development of OW use after its treatment in water-fuel emulsion of boilers and incinerators;
- ❖ development of an integrated method of ES maintenance in open sea.

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